

DETERMINING OPTIMAL REQUEST RATE TO MAINTAIN THERMAL EQUILIBRIUM IN SERVICE-ORIENTED SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

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Abstract: *Service-oriented software architecture is a widely adopted architectural paradigm. This paper explores service-oriented architecture in the context of thermodynamic principles. Recognizing that services consume computational resources and interact via communication channels, we establish a conceptual mapping between key thermodynamic concepts and components of service-oriented systems. Within this framework, we introduce the notion of Service Temperature which is defined as a normalized abstraction of a service's runtime load or operational "stress", as well as Thermal Equilibrium defined as the state in which all interconnected services maintain an equal Service Temperature. Building on this foundation, we develop a mathematical model to determine the optimal request rate necessary to preserve thermal equilibrium. A set of experiments is conducted to validate the mathematical model. The results demonstrate that this approach enables software architects to design service-oriented systems which services are in runtime balance in terms of operational load (i.e., in thermal equilibrium).*

Keywords: *Service-Oriented Architecture, Thermodynamics, Software Metrics, Service Temperature, Service Optimization, Thermal Equilibrium.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Software systems play an important role in nearly every aspect of modern life and are utilized in various industries like communication, transportation, education, healthcare or finance. As these systems grow in scale and complexity, ensuring their non-functional quality requirements like reliability, performance, and adaptability become increasingly essential (Haigh, 2010). Understanding and maintaining an appropriate level of various non-functional requirements can be a complex and ongoing challenge. Achieving an appropriate balance among these requirements requires thoughtful design. In this context, software systems must be carefully architected to support and maintain these non-functional characteristics throughout their lifecycle.

One of the most critical artefacts produced during the software design phase is the software architecture, which serves as the foundational blueprint guiding all subsequent development and system evolution (Washizaki, 2024). Software architecture defines the fundamental concepts and properties of a software system within its environment, as reflected in its elements, their relationships, and the guiding principles of its design and evolution (ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010, 2022; Washizaki, 2024).

Service-oriented software architecture (SOA) represents one possible approach in software architecture design. This paper examines service-oriented software architecture in the context of thermodynamic principles. We have established a conceptual mapping between key thermodynamic concepts and components of service-oriented systems. Based on these mappings, a mathematical model to determine the optimal request rate to maintain thermal equilibrium is defined.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the key concepts of service-oriented architecture and establishes connections with principles from thermodynamics. Section 3 presents the formulation of the mathematical model. In Section 4, numerical results are discussed to illustrate the behaviour of the proposed model. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and outlines directions for future research.

2. SERVICE-ORIENTED SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE AND THERMODYNAMICS

This section introduces the key concepts of service-oriented architecture and establishes their alignment with thermodynamic principles. These insights will form the basis for further modelling.

2.1. Service-Oriented Architecture

There is no single universal software architecture; instead, a wide range of architectural styles, patterns, and models exist to address different system goals and contexts (Hasselbring, 2018; Washizaki, 2024). One approach is service-oriented architecture (SOA), which is based on the principle of designing software as a collection of loosely coupled, reusable, and interoperable services that communicate over a network (Papazoglou & Van Den Heuvel, 2007). SOA promotes modularity and flexibility, making it well-suited for distributed and scalable systems. This approach can be realized in various concrete forms, including Microservice architecture (Alshuqayran et al., 2016), Cell-based architecture (Abeyasinghe, 2025), or Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) serverless architecture (Shahrad et al., 2019) – each offering distinct advantages and trade-offs in terms of scalability, deployment, and granularity of services (Cordingly et al., 2020; de Oliveira Rosa et al., 2020; Ford et al., 2021; Hassan & Bahsoon, 2016).

A conceptual overview of service-oriented architecture is presented in Figure 1. Typically, this architectural approach includes components responsible for service management, such as service registration, discovery, orchestration, and choreography. In addition, a variety of services can be identified, each providing specific functionality. In addition, Figure 1 depicts that each service requires resources for operational work. Although these services are loosely coupled, they can communicate with each other (i.e., *Service A* to *Service C*, and *Service B* to *Service C* in the figure). Communication between services is realized through well-defined interfaces and standardized protocols.

Figure 1: Conceptual overview of a service-oriented architecture

2.2. Thermal Equilibrium in the Context of Software Architecture

Thermodynamics, a fundamental branch of physics, studies the relationships between heat, temperature, work, and energy (Walker, 2017). One of its foundational principles, the Zeroth Law of Thermodynamics, establishes the basis for thermal equilibrium: if System A and System B are each in thermal equilibrium with the System C, they are also in equilibrium with each other (Walker, 2017). This implies that when systems are brought into thermal contact, they will eventually equalize in temperature if no external interference occurs (Walker, 2017).

This principle can be abstracted to the domain of service-oriented software architectures, where a system is composed of a number of interconnected software services (i.e., subsystems). In this context, each service can be seen as a thermodynamic object. Services consume computational resources to perform their operations and interact with one another through communication channels – which can be interpreted as the thermal contacts between subsystems. In this context, we introduce the concept of Service Temperature as a normalized abstraction representing the runtime "stress" or operational load of a service.

Various performance metrics can be used to characterize the operational load of a software service. Each service is typically deployed independently, often within a virtual machine (VM) or a containerized

environment, which provides isolation and allows fine-grained monitoring of resource consumption. In this direction, we will focus on four key software metrics: CPU Utilization, Memory Usage, Latency, and Request Rate:

- CPU Utilization reflects the consumption of processing capacity by a service over time (Pacifici et al., 2008),
- Memory Usage indicates the amount of physical or virtual memory allocated or actively used by the service to perform tasks and related procedures (ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765, 2017),
- Latency represents the time taken from the initiation of a service request and the start of actual processing (ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765, 2017),
- Request Rate corresponds to the number of requests received by the service per unit of time (Shen, 2010).

Given this model, Thermal Equilibrium in the context of service-oriented software architecture is defined as the state in which all interconnected software services maintain the same Service Temperature.

3. MATHEMATICAL MODEL FORMULATION

The main assumptions of the optimization problem under consideration in this paper are:

- The set of interconnected software services is given;
- Service Temperature is calculated as weighted sum of CPU Utilization, Memory Usage, Latency, and Request Rate;
- CPU Utilization, Memory Usage and Latency are known;
- For each service, the Request Rate needs to be determined such that the Service Temperature difference between each pair of services is less than a given small value;
- Temperature variations are allowed but must be minimized.

To formulate mathematical model of the observed optimization problem, the following notation is used:

- S – set of services

Parameters:

- cpu_j – j -th service's CPU utilization, $j \in S$
- mem_j – j -th service's memory usage, $j \in S$
- lat_j – j -th service's latency, $j \in S$
- wc_j – weight (importance) of the j -th service's CPU utilization, $j \in S$
- wm_j – weight of the j -th service's memory usage, $j \in S$
- wl_j – weight of the j -th service's latency, $j \in S$
- wr_j – weight of the j -th service's request rate, $j \in S$
- t_j – service temperature of the j -th service, $j \in S$
- lr_j, ur_j – lower and upper bound of the j -th service's request rate, $j \in S$
- e – required difference between service temperatures

Variables:

- x_j – j -th service's request rate, $j \in S$
- t_j – Service Temperature of the j -th service, $j \in S$
- d_{ij} – deviation variable that represents deviation of required difference between Services Temperature of i -th and j -th services, $i, j \in S, i \neq j$.

For each service $j \in S$, the temperature is calculated as:

$$t_j = wc_j cpu_j + wm_j mem_j + wl_j lat_j + wr_j x_j \quad (1)$$

Thermal Equilibrium between two services $i, j \in S$ is expressed by:

$$|t_i - t_j| \leq e \quad (2)$$

This nonlinear condition can be linearized using the following two conditions:

$$t_i - t_j \leq e \quad (3)$$

$$t_j - t_i \leq e \quad (4)$$

Mathematical model of the described optimization problem can now be formulated as follows:

$$\min f(x) = \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{j \in S, j \neq i} d_{ij} \quad (5)$$

s.t.

$$t_j = wc_j cpu_j + wm_j mem_j + wl_j lat_j + wr_j x_j, j \in S \quad (6)$$

$$t_i - t_j - d_{ij} = 0, i, j \in S, i \neq j \quad (7)$$

$$lr_j \leq x_j \leq ur_j, j \in S \quad (8)$$

$$x_j \in \mathbb{Z}, j \in S \quad (9)$$

The objective (5) represents the sum of all deviations, that should be minimal. The constraint (6) refers to the connection between the variables related to the service temperature and the request rate. The constraint (7) is the linearisation of the thermal equilibrium condition (2), additionally extended with deviations variables. The last two constraints are related to the boundaries of the services' request rates and their integer nature.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Six groups of experiments were conducted to examine the dimensions of the formulated problem that can be solved exactly. The number of services in these experiments were: 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30. For each dimension, ten instances of data was generated. The summarized values of metrics are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Input data for the optimizations

Metrics	Min	Max	Weight
CPU Utilization	45%	100%	1
Memory Usage	45%	100%	1
Latency	20ms	44ms	0.01

In all instances of all six dimensions, the parameter e is set to zero, lower and upper bounds of request rate are 1000 and 5000, and the weight of request rate is set to 0.1.

All optimizations were performed on a laptop computer with 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i5 and 16 GB of RAM. Problems were solved in GLPK modelling environment using combination of four methods: mixed cover cuts, Gomory's mixed integer cuts, MIR (mixed integer rounding) cuts, and clique cuts. The optimization time was limited to 600 seconds.

Table 2 gives the main data about optimization results. In the columns Objective, the average values of the objective, i.e. sum of deviations and their standard deviation are shown. In the column No of optimal solution, the number of instanced which have been solved exactly within time limitation is given. The column Time gives the average optimization time and their standard deviations. The last column (Deviations) contains the average and maximal values of deviations. For instances that could not be solved exactly, the results obtained after 600 seconds are shown.

Table 2: Summarized optimization results

No of services	Objective		No of optimal solution	Time (sec)		Deviations	
	average	SD		average	SD	average	max
5	0.296	0.073	10	8.20	7.01	0.0148	0.056
10	1.369	0.097	10	145.39	107.70	0.0152	0.076
15	3.144	0.325	4	340.53	170.81	0.0150	0.082
20	5.757	0.323	1	442.90		0.0152	0.086
25	8.840	0.648	0			0.0147	0.087
30	13.204	0.878	0			0.0152	0.087

The first conclusion based on Table 2 is that the possibility of an exact solution decreases rapidly with increasing problem dimensions, i.e. the number of services. Given that the number of services in many software systems may vary depending on the application domain and the level of service granularity, heuristics need to be developed to solve real-world problems. On the other hand, even in cases where an optimal solution was not obtained, the quality of the solutions obtained after 600 seconds is very good. The average and maximum deviation values are similar to those in the optimal solutions. This suggests that in most of these instances an optimal solution was found, but that the search process could not be completed within the given time limit.

As expected, the average value of the objective increases with increasing dimensions, i.e. with increasing the number of services. The relatively small standard deviation of the value of the objective in ten instances indicates robustness, i.e. that the solution is reliable regardless of input data variations.

5. CONCLUSION

Software architecture is one of the key artefacts defined in software design phase. This research has introduced a conceptual mapping between fundamental thermodynamic principles and components of service-oriented systems, leading to the development of a mathematical model for determining the optimal request rate required to maintain thermal equilibrium. These findings enable software architects to design systems in which services are balanced at runtime with respect to their operational load. Additionally, the proposed model supports the detection of imbalance in terms of service temperature, providing a foundation for informed architectural decisions (e.g., allocation of additional resources, deallocation of resources, service composition, service decomposition, etc.).

Future research may explore models where examined software metrics are no longer fixed, allowing dynamic adaptation. In addition, the model can be extended to incorporate a broader set of software metrics to characterize the operational load of a software service. Finally, heuristics will be developed for solving problems of realistic dimensions, given the small dimensions of the problem that can be solved exactly.

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